

U.S. ARMY COMBAT CAPABILITIES DEVELOPMENT COMMAND ARMY RESEARCH LABORATORY

Influence of Consolidation Pressure on Tensile Strength of Ultra High
Molecular Weight Polyethylene Composites

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- ❑ Ultra High Molecular Weight Polyethylene UHMWPE is unique for its low density and high tensile strength
- ❑ It is light weight and provides higher protection
- ❑ This is used in high velocity impact resistant applications: **protective shields, armored vehicles, helmets, bulletproof vests, short arrest systems for aircraft**

Goal of the Program

Goal: Understand how consolidation process variables Temperature (T), Pressure (P) and time (t) control composite microstructure (*Reduce voids, Increase fiber volume fraction, Minimize filament damage*) to improve composite performance (*Reduce weight, Maintain Performance, Reduce dynamic deflection, Maximize energy absorption*).

Scale

Consolidated Panel

Sheets: ~200 μm

Virgin SK99 Fibers

Filament: 10-20 μm

AFM Images of Microtomed Post-Draw Fibers

Fibril : ~10-100 nm

Molecule (atomic)

OBJECTIVES:

- ❑ Study the tensile strength of UHMWPE composites as a function of consolidation pressure
- ❑ Study the void fraction and thickness reduction as a function of consolidation pressure
- ❑ Study the consolidation pressure induced micro damage on the UHMWPE sheet composites
- ❑ To understand the tension failure modes and damage mechanisms
- ❑ To have a correlation of fiber strength to [0/90/0/90] sheet strength taking void and compressive strain into account
- ❑ To have insight on how to improve the Tension performance of this material

APPROACH:

- ❑ To develop an experimental methodology for tension test of UHMWPE composites
- ❑ To develop lab scale consolidation of UHMWPE following the exact thermal and pressure profile prescribed by DSM Dyneema
- ❑ To perform tension test on **unconsolidated** HB210 UHMWPE thin sheets and composites **consolidated** at various pressures [1ksi, 2ksi,3ksi, 6.5ksi,8.25ksi & 10ksi]
- ❑ Consolidation pressure induced micro damage analysis
- ❑ Results and discussions

Overview of the Test Methods

IFSS: Interfacial shear strength

- Vertical load applied
- Specimen failed in tension
- Include tension and in plane shear

- Include tension, in plane shear, punch shear which are useful for studying mixed loading that occurs during impact

- Tension properties can be achieved directly from axial tension of sheets
- It enables effects of consolidation pressure on microstructure and tension properties to be quantified
- Challenge is the slippage in the grip

2D Thick-Section Penetration Mechanics

DOP Testing

Development of Tension Experiment

- ❑ Instron: 1331
- ❑ Load cell: 100kN
- ❑ Grips: Hydraulic
- ❑ Clamp Pressure: 2ksi
- ❑ Displacement rate = 0.05 in/min

Specimen prep

All pieces have been assembled and kept in place with the help of tape

Specimen Dimensions:

- ❑ Specimen Length : $L = 5.64''$ [1.32" Spacer + 3" Sample + 1.32" Spacer]
- ❑ Width $W = 0.5''$
- ❑ Thickness $T = 0.157 \pm 0.006$ mm
- ❑ Tab: $L = 2.32''$
 $W = 0.6''$
- ❑ Gage Length = 1"
- ❑ Specimen & Spacers are Consolidated at same Pressure

Tensile Strength vs Clamp pressure

Load vs Displacement of Tension Test with Gage Length GL = 1", 2" & 3"

Consolidation Process of 1L Dyneema Sheets

- Pressure Source: Instron 4484, Load Cell: 150kN
- Heat source: Environmental Chamber
- Two identical Metal platens have been used on top and bottom
- Both the setup and the material stack arranged in a symmetric way
- No noticeable temperature gradient through the thickness of the stack with & without separation film [release film]
- Oven air temperature is recorded to validate oven screen temperature and found to be identical
- Temperature along the width of the sample recorded 0.25" & 0.5" inside from the edge location of the middle layer and found to be the same

□ Pressure films have been used on the top & bottom layer which show uniform pressure distribution

Material Under Study: Dyneema HB210

HB210 Material Rolled out

- ❑ Crease density 35/foot on the Roll

Every crease is not similarly severe & all the creases are not continuous from one edge to the other in the gage section of the samples

- ❑ Lots of Crease visible on the unconsolidated Dyneema HB210 surface
- ❑ Crease density 4/inch on a 3" X 1" sample
- ❑ Crease direction is parallel to transverse direction
- ❑ Roll samples have crease defects but not transverse samples
- ❑ Crease kinks introduce more voids in the material
- ❑ Resin Reach & resin Lean Areas are Observed inside the $[0/90/0/90]_1$ Sheet

Roll direction test video

- ❑ Fails progressively [these samples have crease effect]
- ❑ Fibers fail in a cluster at a location then another location, then another location & eventually catastrophic failure happens at the end

➤ Transverse samples have been picked to study the effect of consolidation pressure on tensile strength to avoid the effect of original crease defects

- Roll direction samples show 7% strength reduction due to creases
- Transverse sample is least sensitive for creases

Transverse direction test video

- ❑ Fails instantaneously [these samples don't have crease defect in the load carrying fibers]
- ❑ In some cases, fiber failure initiates in a cluster at a location but in a moment catastrophic failure happens all over

Representative Failure Modes in Pictures

Transverse direction tested sample

Tested sample pulled in loading direction separates into two pieces as above pictures

- ❑ Sample surface with fibers parallel to the loading direction shows catastrophic failure
- ❑ but surface with fibers perpendicular to loading direction don't show failure as they don't carry load

Roll direction tested sample

Load vs Displacement & Stress vs Strain Plots of UHMWPE

Unconsolidated

Consolidated @3ksi

Consolidated @10ksi

Load
vs
Displacement

Stress
Vs
Strain

More Progressive Failure Happens to Materials Consolidated at Higher Pressure

Sheet Surface Roughness Study

Thickness of 1 Layer sheet – 2* surface roughness = Roughness free thickness of the sheet

3ksi-top-surface Rz = 51 um

3ksi-bot-surface Rz = 56 um

Micrometer T = 157 um

- Confocal roughness Rz of HB210 sheet shows that the surface has hills and valleys

- roughness free thickness is required to get accurate tensile strength

- Micrometer measurement of thickness includes the surface roughness

- Thickness of 24 Layer stack includes 2 rough surfaces
- Total thickness of 24 counts of 1 individual Layer sheet has 48 rough surfaces
- Average roughness of one surface can be calculated from the above two micrometer measurements

Consolidation Pressure	[Unconsolidated]	1ksi	2-ksi	3-ksi	8.25-ksi	10-ksi
Single sheet roughness, R_{avg} , microns	24 ± 5	22 ± 4	23 ± 3	20 ± 5	16 ± 5	19 ± 5
Roughness free thickness, um	167 ± 7	146 ± 4	140 ± 4	135 ± 4	135 ± 5	130 ± 3

- ❑ Gas Pycnometer provides Skeletal volume
- ❑ Archimedes method provides external volume
- ❑ Void fraction can be calculated from these two volume

consolidation Pressure	Void Fraction	uncertainty of Void Fraction
1ksi	7	1
2ksi	4	1
3ksi	4	1
8.25ksi	6	1
10ksi	7	1
Unconsolidated	19	1

- Challenges with Archimedes' Principal:**
- TPU is hydrophilic
 - Sample sucks in water
 - external volume gets compromised

Solution:

- ❑ Applying paraffin coat on the material to prevent water suction
- ❑ The volume of a piece of glass slide has been measured using Archimedes principal to validate the process

Tensile Strength & Evolution of Pressure Induced Damage

Strength $\sigma = \frac{1}{2}V_f X_f (1 - V_v)$

[Contribution of matrix is not included in the equation]

where

σ = Tensile strength of 4 layer sheet

V_f = fiber volume fraction

V_v = the void fraction

X_f = Fiber tensile strength

- Processing condition that guarantees higher void and thickness reduction without any pressure induced denting, flattening, spilling may increase tensile strength to some extent

21 MPa consolidated HB210-1 layer [0/90/0/90] sheet shows fiber-fiber contact imprints which is in the form of dents are more frequent and severe than unconsolidated material

- Void reduction benefits get defeated by pressure induced damage in fibers for consolidation pressure more than 21 MPa

50% Fiber failure strength has been used in the calculation

Fiber layers of [0/90/0/90] sheets have been peeled off and looked under SEM

Consolidation pressure, MPa	[Unconsolidated]	7	14	21	46	58	70
Experimental Avg. strength, MPa	1157±50	1274±56	1368±57	1430±56	1391±64	1374±61	1392±73
Calculated Strength, MPa	1454	1668	1703	1705	1662	1640	1617

Measurement of fiber width growth & fiber surface flattening

- **2W = Width of the compressed fiber in the sheet**
- **2b = Flatness width on the surface of a fiber in the sheet**

Material	Avg. 2b, um	Avg. 2W, um
SK-99 fibers	0	11.61 ± 1.65 [200+]
Unconsolidated	6.85 ± 2.79[17]	12.50 ± 1.42[250+]
7 MPa	8.87 ± 1.87 [180+]	13.29 ± 1.74[220]
21 MPa	9.12 ± 2.21[150+]	13.90 ± 1.80[250+]
70 MPa	11.28 ± 3.17 [150+]	15.34 ± 2.06 [340+]

- ❑ **Width 2w of a fiber & the flatness 2b on the surface of a fiber inside the [0/90/0/90] sheet grows as a function of consolidation pressure**
- ❑ **Growth of fiber width is restricted by adjacent fibers and matrix**
- ❑ **Growth in width causes splitting and separation of fibril bundles in a fiber which may result is early failure there**

NOTE: [count of measurements]

Measurement of Imprints & Surface deformation

Fiber layers of [0/90/0/90] sheets have been peeled off and looked under SEM & all measurements are conducted on the SEM images

Material	Area % under pressure on fibers	Length % having imprint
SK-99 Virgin fiber	0	0
Unconsolidated	7	2 [17]
7 MPa	55	8 [250+]
21 MPa	59	19 [250+]
70 MPa	75	0

NOTE: [count of measurements]

- Percentage of the length occupied by all imprints on all the fibers in an image has been calculated and plotted as a function of consolidation pressure which shows a linear increase and it is 100% at 70 MPa
- The area percentage on the fiber surface inside a sheet that experience pressure is counted and found to increase as a function of consolidation pressure. 75 % of the total area experience pressure at 70 MPa

Determination of Sheet Strength Using Void fraction & Strain

Residual Tensile Strength as a Function of Fiber Compressive Strain

Fiber Strain distribution @ different Processing Pressure

- Fiber strain has been calculated using the deformation geometry of the compressed fibers
- Figure:1 shows the strain distribution @ different processing pressure
- Figure : 2 uses 50% fiber strain from Figure : 1
- Figure : 3 uses UHMWPE fiber residual strength data from literature
- Figure : 2, Figure : 3, Figure : 4 have been used to calculate sheet tensile strength

processing pressure		processing pressure		Fiber strength at 50% failure probability		sheet tensile strength	
ksi	Mpa	void %	strain % FVF	Vf	strength %	residual strength Xf	Mpa
0	0	0.19	0.306	0.83	0.90	4327.54	1454
0.1	0.7	0.17	0.307	0.83	0.90	4326.11	1496
0.2	1.4	0.15	0.309	0.83	0.90	4324.68	1530
0.3	2.1	0.13	0.310	0.83	0.90	4323.25	1560
0.4	2.8	0.12	0.311	0.83	0.90	4321.83	1584
0.5	3.5	0.10	0.312	0.83	0.90	4320.40	1605
0.6	4.2	0.09	0.314	0.83	0.90	4318.97	1623
0.7	4.9	0.09	0.315	0.83	0.90	4317.55	1637

Sheet Tensile Strength @ % of Fiber Failure

$0.50 * X_f$

$0.20 * X_f$

$0.18 * X_f$

- Sheet tensile strength has been calculated using different % of fiber failure probability

- Fiber failure strength at 18% failure probability estimates sheet strength matching to experimental data
- This indicates that 18% fibers failure initiates catastrophic failure in the sheet
- There could be other mechanism responsible for lower experimental strength at consolidation pressures less than 21 MPa

Summary & Conclusion:

- An Experimental methodology for tension test of Dyneema thin composites has been developed
- A lab-scale manufacturing technique has been developed to make Dyneema composites following the exact DSM provided thermal and pressure profile
- Void fraction as a function of consolidation has been determined
- Evolution of micro damage inside the sheet as a function of consolidation pressure has been studied
- A competing mechanism is found where tensile strength increases with increase in consolidation pressure due to void reduction and thickness reduction but it shows a reduction at higher pressure due to pressure induced damage like flattening, splitting, denting
- A correlation has been established to get UHMWPE sheet tensile strength using single fiber strength taking sheet void reduction and fiber compressive strain into account as a function of consolidation pressure
- Processing condition that guarantees higher void and thickness reduction without any pressure induced denting, flattening, splitting may increase tensile strength to some extent**

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QUESTIONS ?

